

ANALYTICAL STUDY OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract

Examining the levels of occupational stress endured by J&K physical education instructors was the goal of the current study. 288 individuals who taught physical education in secondary schools in J&K made up the sample. The Occupational Stress Index was given to the respondents (Shrivastava and Singh, 1984). With certain adjustments, this Occupational Stress Index is employed. With the assistance of tools called SPSS 17.0, the data were examined. According to the study's findings, occupational stress among physical education instructors is typically moderate in terms of both its individual components and as a whole. Only job ambiguity and unprofitability significantly reduced stress levels in physical education teachers. The topic of easing instructors of physical education's stress has been brought up.

Keywords: Occupational stress, Physical education teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The verifiable viewpoint of actual schooling is no more. Today, gigantic advancements have occurred in this field at the worldwide level. Today, actual instruction educators are playing various different as well as particular jobs as instructors, authorities, coordinators and overseers. It isn't not difficult to energize and rouse the understudies to sports exercises. "The exercises and errands performed by an instructor of actual schooling might be partitioned into five classifications; in particular preparation, educating, assessing, regulatory and different unclassified obligations". He has the obligation to assist the understudies with creating abilities, ace information and secure mentalities and social characteristics that assist an individual with turning into all that he/she is prepared to do. The obligations of actual training educators have expanded manifolds in present day logical age. "According to hopeful perspective, an actual instruction instructor should have devotion towards calling, readiness of body and brain, movability, drive, qualification for work, discipline, energy, truthfulness, poise, friendliness, very engine limit, comical inclination, honor, pride, self-assurance, fairness, informative abilities, athlete's soul and so on. He should be a model for his understudies and partners with respect to his personality, direct and conduct" (Kamlesh, 2002) [6]. With the adjustment of the idea of actual schooling, the job of the actual training educators has gone past the jungle gym and entered the homeroom instructing. Current actual instruction perceives its liability regarding man's all out advancement i.e., physical, mental, instructive and scholarly. Because of these obligations the actual schooling instructors work is more unpleasant. To figure out their feeling of anxiety the specialist has arranged and led an investigation of the optional school actual instruction instructors. Showing in actual schooling is an astonishing and testing calling that consolidates study hall abilities with accentuation on greatness in sports. The actual instruction educators while playing various different as well as specific jobs as instructors, authorities, coordinators and directors effectively become inclined to work pressure. Work pressure among actual training educators working in schools has gotten the consideration of specialists during the most recent couple of years. The pressure in school educating has not been another subject all around the world including India. The aftereffects of the review would assist with figuring out the degree/level of word related pressure among the actual training educators working in different kinds of schools in Meerut Locale of Uttar Pradesh State. The outcomes would likewise assist with figuring out the variables answerable for word related pressure among actual schooling instructors.

The review may be helpful in recognizing the degrees of stress of the educators as connected with the three factors.

Review of Literature

Tam and Mong (2005) showed work pressure implies individuals experience mental state which is incongruence and nonconformist between laborer's view of the requests on them and their capacity to adapt to those interest. "On account of instructor stress, it is utilized to portray 'an interest made upon the versatile limits of the psyche and body... which whenever went on past the capacity of these abilities to answer, prompts the physical and mental weariness and potentially a definitive breakdown alluded to by Seyle" (Fontana, 1989) . Konukman, Agbuga and Erdogan (2010) viewed pressure as related with job struggle. The review uncovered that educating and training are two distinct word related jobs, each having explicit pressure and burnout issues. These two distinct jobs when performed together out come into job struggle and accordingly work pressure among Actual Instruction educators who additionally mentor.

Verma (1997) explored the work pressure and occupation fulfilment of actual training educators working in Govt., Private and State funded schools of U.T. Chandigarh. He found tremendous distinction between actual schooling educators working in govt. furthermore, state funded schools in their work pressure and occupation fulfilment. Actual training educators working in Govt., and Tuition based schools were additionally observed to be fundamentally disparate in their work pressure and occupation fulfilment. Sharma (2000) directed a near report on 110 male school actual training educators of Himachal Pradesh, Punjab and Association Region Chandigarh in work pressure, work fulfilment and change factors. The review uncovered that Actual Training educators of Himachal Pradesh State experienced more work pressure than their partners in Punjab State and Association Region Chandigarh. Be that as it may, no tremendous distinction was seen in their scholar and general climate, proficient relationship in training educators working in Punjab and Chandigarh were found better compared to educators working in the universities of Himachal Pradesh. Educators of actual training working in Punjab and Chandigarh were viewed as generally preferred changed over the educators working in the State Himachal Pradesh. Rathod (2006) concentrate on work pressure of actual training educators showed tendency towards 'moderate work pressure'. The alumni just educators, educators working in neighbourhood body's schools, instructors working in young ladies just schools have communicated more work pressure. The more seasoned matured actual instruction educators have communicated more work pressure. The instructors with lesser experience and profoundly experienced have communicated more prominent work pressure.

Methods and Material

Sample

288 teachers from government, nonprofit, and for-profit schools in Jammu and Kashmir U.T. made up the study's sample. 288 school physical education instructors in J&K have replied overall.

Tools occupational stress File by Shrivastava and Singh (1984) was the base to direct to survey the degree of stress among the actual instruction instructors. Fundamentally the scale comprises of 46 things, each connected on the five focuses scale. As the scale is general in nature so the specialists have been altered the list in connecting with the actual training. Two distinct examples of scoring have embraced for two kinds of things. For genuine things, emphatically deviate - 1, dissent - 2, uncertain - 3, concur - 3, firmly concur - 5 and misleading keyed things, the converse parts of the gig life, which cause pressure in one way or others, for example, job over-burden, job vagueness, job struggle, bunch and political strain, obligation regarding people, under cooperation, feebleness, unfortunate friend relations, characteristic improvement, low status, demanding working circumstances, and un-productivity.

Procedure The physical education instructors received the questionnaire directly from me. The researcher has given a briefing on why the study is being done. The respondents were given enough time to properly read and comprehend the questions before responding, as opposed to providing a canned response.

Scoring and Analysis

To determine the relevance of the various measures of subclasses of occupational stress among physical education instructors, the chi-square test was used in the current study.

The occupational stress index's mean scores for each subscale are shown in Table 1, along with the results of the chisquare test.

1. **Role Overload:** Overall, we discover that 67.7% of the sampled population experiences moderate levels of stress, 27.8% experience low levels of stress, and just 4.5% experience severe levels of stress. The majority of the group exhibited moderate levels of role overload, as seen by the substantial difference between these three categories of stress shown by the chi-square test ($X^2 = 176.52$; $P = .000$).
2. **Role Ambiguity:** It was noted that the bulk of the sample showed lower levels of role ambiguity (50.7%), which was closely followed by moderate levels of role ambiguity (5.9%), and very few of the selected sample showed high levels of role ambiguity. Chisquare test found a significant difference between these groups of frequencies, with low and moderate levels of frequencies being high ($X^2 = 99.81$; $P = .000$).
3. **Role Conflict:** A Chi-square test with an X^2 value of 141.44 and a P value =.000 showed a significant difference between low, moderate, and high levels of role conflict. The table shows that the majority of them (56.6%) reported moderate levels of stress, followed by 42% who reported low levels of stress, and the remaining 1.4% who reported high levels of role conflict, which was determined to be statistically significant.
4. **Unreasonable group pressure and political pressure:** Overall, we find that 79.27% of the sampled population experiences moderate levels of stress, 15.3% experience low levels of stress, and just 5.6% experience high levels of stress. Furthermore, the chi-square test showed a significant difference ($X^2 = 276.33$; $P = .000$) between all three types of stress, demonstrating that the majority of the sample experienced Political Pressure & Unreasonable Group Stress at moderate levels.
5. **Low Status:** In terms of low status, it was found that the majority of the sample had moderate levels of stress (59.4%), followed by high levels of stress (29.4%), and that the remaining sample had low levels of low status (10.8%). The chi-square test showed a significant difference ($X^2 = 103.65$; $P = .000$) between these sets of frequencies, with moderate and high levels of frequencies present.

Primary discoveries of the current review are:

Altogether word related pressure, larger part of the actual schooling instructors experienced moderate degrees of stress, trailed by elevated degrees of stress and not many of them encountered lower levels of pressure. In subcomponents of word related pressure Job overburden, Job struggle, Outlandish gathering and Political Strain, Obligation regarding people, Under support, Weakness, Unfortunate friend relations, Characteristic impoverishment, low status, and difficult working circumstances, larger part of the respondents communicated moderate degrees of stress. Just in 2 parts of word related pressure job equivocalness and unfruitfulness, actual training educators experienced lower levels of pressure.

Al-Mohammadi and Capel (2006) directed their review so as to recognize the reasons for pressure among actual training educators in Qatar and furthermore to make sense of any distinctions in pressure as per: orientation, identity, kind of school and experience. Results showed that there were various reasons for pressure for various gatherings of educators which could be connected with various foundations and encounters and various jobs and obligations in the public eye because of various social and social assumptions and ecological variables. In India, the significant purposes behind encountering pressure among actual schooling educators could be compensation, low status and under cooperation. Indeed, even today, actual schooling educators are paid less when contrasted with educators who show different subjects in the homerooms. Numerous multiple times the arrangements are simply transitory, which adds to existing weight. Further, the actual schooling educators are given extra liabilities in their organizations, since they are 'free' during working hours. Infact, the responsibility will be

something else for them when contrasted with different educators, as they need to come early and leave late from their separate foundations. Again these actual training educators essentially experience low status in their foundation as well as outside the organization contrasted with different educators. The actual instruction instructors work is generally thought to be as 2nd grade work contrasted with scholastic educators. Because of these there will be lesser work fulfillment among actual training instructors, which further expands their pressure.

To decrease pressure among actual training educators not many of the exercises could be arranged. Unwinding practices like JPMR (Jacobson's Solid Unwinding Treatment) or JAPMR (Jacobson's High level Strong Unwinding Treatment) could be rehearsed by the educators. Yoga, reflection, 63 going through pressure the executives programs are different choices to lessen the pressure in a powerful manner. Finally educationists and strategy producers ought to design suitable and successful measures to decrease the pressure by embracing easy to use ways to deal with work on the way of life of actual instruction instructors, where one can anticipate best result from these actual schooling educators.

Table 1: Frequency and Percent of Teachers Falling under Different Categories of Stress Levels in Various Components of Occupational Stress Index

Variable	F/ %	Low	Levels Moderate	High	Chi-square/P value
Role overload	F	80	195	13	$X^2 = 176.52;$
	%	27.8	67.7	4.5	P=.000
Role ambiguity	F	146	125	17	$X^2 = 99.81;$
	%	50.7	43.4	5.9	P=.000
Role conflict	F	121	163	4	$X^2 = 141.44 ;$
	%	42.0	56.6	1.4	P = .000
Unreasonable Group & Political Pressure	F	44	228	16	$X^2 = 276.33;$
	%	15.3	79.2	5.6	P = .000
Responsibility for persons	F	76	160	52	$X^2 = 67.00 ;$
	%	26.4	55.6	18.1	P = .000
Under participation	F	85	177	26	$X^2 = 176.52;$
	%	29.5	61.5	9	P=.000
Powerlessness	F	42	200	46	$X^2 = 169.08;$
	%	14.6	69.4	16	P=.000
Poor peer relations	F	20	161	107	$X^2 = 105.44 ;$
	%	6.9	55.9	37.2	P=.000
Intrinsic impoverishment	F	76	163	49	$X^2 = 73.94;$
	%	26.4	56.6	17	P = .000
Low status	F	31	171	86	$X^2 = 103.65;$
	%	10.8	59.4	29.9	P=.000
Strenuous working conditions	F	78	170	40	$X^2 = 93.08;$
	%	27.1	59	13.9	P = .000
Unprofitability	F	159	128	1	$X^2 = 146.02;$
	%	55.2	44.4	0.3	P = .000

Total occupational stress	F	31	171	86	$X^2 = 103.65;$
	%	10.8	59.4	29.9	P =.000

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